

ULTRASONICS INSPECTIONS AND CONFOCAL MICROSCOPY TO EVALUATE FATIGUE DAMAGE IN FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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1 Abstract

On this study, periodic ultrasonic inspections were performed during flexural fatigue tests, on two different composites, and under certain conditions a confocal microscope proved useful to evaluate surface damage detected by acoustic signal analysis. Rectangular bars of plain weave glass fiber/phenolic resin composite and bars of a specific sequence of carbon fiber/epoxy resin composite were subjected to four-point bending fatigue tests until reaching 20,000 cycles, but stopping every 2,000 cycles for ultrasound inspection. Software was developed to create C-scan images, but also to process each A-scan signal through one of several algorithms that helped spot internal and surface damage. The tests using the glass fiber/resin composite allowed observing the damage before failure as seen by acoustic signal analysis. The tests on the carbon fiber/resin composite showed that ultrasound can aid to pinpoint where surface damage might be occurring and where a confocal microscope can be used. The confocal microscope can quantitatively record micro topographical surface roughness caused by points of contact. The study showed that acoustic signal analysis plus confocal microscopy can be effectively used to monitor internal and surface damage under flexural fatigue of two different polymer matrix composites.

2 Introduction

The analyses of several scan images (A-scan, B-scan, C-scan, etc.) are often necessary to assure the integrity of a Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) or in Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) components. One of the aims of this study was to improve damage detection, by creating alternative scan images that can summarize internal and superficial damage in one single image, and thus reduce inspection analysis time. The procedure performed by Mouritz et al. [1] was used to generate flexural fatigue damage, but with two other composites, and this time with the aid of an encoded ultrasound scan. Although ultrasound inspections are used to detect internal discontinuities, surface irregularities can produce contrast spots, and here a confocal microscope was employed to examine the surface damage. In the past confocal microscopy had been shown to be useful in quantifying the print-through or surface roughness caused by residual shrinkage of the resin on some GFRP [2]. The other aim of this study was to explore the capability of confocal microscopy in quantifying superficial composite damage.

3 Experimental procedure

Two different composite materials were subjected to four-point bending fatigue tests. Specimens were rectangular bars of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy, and bars of phenolic resin reinforced with plain weave glass fiber. The specimens were inspected using immersion ultrasound every 2,000 cycles, until reaching 20,000 cycles. The water bath and scanner were designed and built by Mapro using a Socomate USPC3100LA ultrasound acquisition card. C-scan images were produced in addition to other composed scan images, which resulted after applying different algorithms to each pulse-echo A-scan signal. The software application to process the pulse-echo signals and data visualization was developed also by Mapro using the LabView platform from National Instruments.

The pre-impregnated fiber used to build the CFRP was Hexcel 8552/32%/134/IM7(12K), where 32% refers to the amount of 8552 resin, 134 is the approximate ply thickness in μm , and 12,000 is the amount of IM7 carbon fibers per tow. The laminated CFRP specimens were design by Mapro and CTM, and built by the INTA Materials and Structures Department. The three CFRP thicknesses tested are assumed to produce comparable results, because the selected stacking sequences have approximately the same orientation distributions, as Table 1 explains. The GFRP was Isovid G-3, which was supplied by Composites Ate, and consisted of plain weave 200g/m² fiber glass with a modified phenolic resin that enhances its flame retardant characteristics. Layers were 0.10-0.11mm thick, and were stacked to match 0° and 90°.

The tests followed the guidelines of ASTM standard D6272 for flexural properties of plastics by four-point bending. Table 2 shows the dimensions of the CFRP and GFRP bars along with the spans used during testing. Two deviations from the recommendations of standard D6272 did occur; one

was that the width of the specimens was larger than 25mm and secondly that the support and load spans of CFRP specimens, and specimens GFRP-P011, did not follow the span-to-thickness ratio of 32 to 1. The width of 40mm was selected to allow enough volume of material to be inspected in a water bath by a pulse-echo 1MHz (\varnothing 13mm crystal) ultrasonic probe. The gain was set at 15dB for all inspections, except for specimens CFRP-P041, where a 5MHz (\varnothing 10mm crystal) probe at 5dB was used. The signal output voltage remained at 240V.

The span-to-thickness did not conform exactly to standard D6272, because the cured CFRP specimens were thinner than expected and the tool used to align and separate the loading support noses had already been built. The alignment fixture tool, which was recommended by the standard, helped assure all 4 points were at the same relative position every time fatigue cycles had to be renewed. Throughout manufacture and testing the specimens were designated not only using the name that appears in Tables 1 and 2, but also using their nominal dimensions, and a number to distinguish them, for example: CFRP-P041-40-307-8_2/2.

The fatigue tests were performed using a 250kN MTS 322 Test Frame at a frequency of 0.8Hz. A specimen of each type of material was tested to determine the maximum strength, σ_0 . Test loads were calculated to produce a normalized fatigue stress in the range 0.2 to 0.9 for GFRP specimens and in the range 0.36 to 0.60 for CFRP.

Normalized fatigue stress is defined as the maximum flexural fatigue stress in the outer layers of the laminate, σ_{max} , divided by the maximum flexural strength of the outer layers of the composite, σ_0 . In the course of testing, some normalized fatigue stresses were varied, but these inconsistencies did not affect the useful information drawn from the experimental results. The minimum to maximum fatigue stress ratio R was of 0.1.

Table 1. Stacking sequences and percentages of layers oriented 90°, 0° or \pm 45°.

Specimen	Stacking sequence	% 90°	% 0°	% 45°	% -45°
CFRP-P011	$[(0/\pm 45/0_2/\pm 45/0_2/90) / (0_2/\pm 45/0_2/\pm 45/0_2/\overline{90})]_{12}s$	8.8	54.4	18.4	18.4
CFRP-P021	$[(0/90) / (0_2/\pm 45/0_2/\pm 45/0_2/\overline{90})]_9s$	9.5	54.7	17.9	17.9
CFRP-P041	$[(0/90/0/\pm 45/0_2/90) / (0_2/\pm 45/0_2/\pm 45/0_2/\overline{90})]_2s$	11.9	54.2	16.9	16.9

Table 2. Specimen dimensions, and spans used for support and load.

Specimen	Number of Specimens	Length (mm)	Width, <i>W</i> (mm)	Thickness, <i>h</i> (mm)	Support span, <i>L</i> (mm)	Load span, <i>S</i> (mm)
CFRP-P011	2	1440	40.2-40.3	36.5-36.6	1216	608
CFRP-P021	2	1040	40.0	26.0-26.1	864	432
CFRP-P041	2	307	40.1	7.9	256	128
GFRP-P011	3	1000	40.0-40.4	38.0-38.3	864	432
GFRP-P021	3	1000	40.0-40.2	27.0-27.8	864	432
GFRP-P031	6	710	40.0-40.1	16.1-16.3	512	256
GFRP-P041	2	307	40.1	8.1	256	128

At 20,000 cycles, a GFRP specimen was inspected using the penetrating liquid technique, which would color cracks in red, and tested until 22,079 cycles, inspected using ultrasounds, and tested again. After 26,079 cycles the ultrasound inspection prompted to use a confocal microscope to inspect the surface. Upon fracture the red coloring was expected to show the shape of the delaminations and thus indicate which image algorithm works best. The phenolic resin in the Isovid G-3 is initially color yellow, but sun light turns the resin brown. However, the interior remains yellow. The red coloring was expected to show a visible contrast with the yellow interior, when the specimen was to fracture. One CFRP specimen was also inspected after 20,000 cycles. The micro topographical images were produced using a Sensofar Plμ2300 confocal microscope.

4 Results

Stress at the outer layers, σ , was calculated using the load, *F*, and conditions described in Table 2, such that $\sigma = (3FL)/(4Wh^2)$. The maximum flexural strength, σ_0 , for specimen CFRP-P041-40-307-8_1/2 was 1135MPa and for GFRP-P031-40-710-16_1/6 was 391MPa. None of the CFRP specimens broke, but C-scan images did show superficial damage at the point in contact with the loading noses. Several GFRP specimens broke, which allowed creating a partial σ_{max} versus cycles to failure plot [3] that suggests that when flexural fatigue is considered the Isovid G-3 should be stressed at values below 235MPa.

Specimen GFRP-P031-40-710-16_5/6 broke at cycle 4001 (Fig. 1a), following the ultrasound inspection at cycle 4000, which allowed observing internal damage just before failure. A typical A-scan, when a

low frequency transducer needs to be used, consists of larger multi-peak interface (I) echo and a smaller multi-peak back-wall (B) echo. If only the B echo is registered, then the resultant C-scan image can be seen in Fig. 1b, which shows some contrast spots. With the aim to observe the most types of damage in one single image, different alternative algorithms were applied to each A-scan to create additional scan images, which will be called \int -scans. Figure 1c shows the result of calculating the area under the A-scan signal (intensity versus depth) for every (x, y) coordinate. Figure 1d shows the integral of the A-scan signal of every (x, y) minus the area of the I and B echoes. Likewise Figs. 1e and f show the \int -scan with the I & B echoes minus the mean, and the \int -scan without the I & B echoes minus the mean. The \int -scans show contrast spots that coincide with damage caused by the upper points of contact (i.e. the two vertical spots), but also other spots appear. Both Fig. 1c and 1f show a large spot to the left side of the bar, and after analyzing B-scans and the broken specimen itself, the spot appears to belong to a delamination near the interface (echo) surface. However the main crack seems to have originated from one of the upper points of contact (Fig. 1a). Although many more trials should be performed, the authors believe the algorithm that shows the most damage information would be the \int -scan without the I & B echoes (Fig. 1d), because clearly brings into contrast both the damage caused by the upper points of contact and also the delamination on the opposite side. The large spot that runs along the right side of Fig. 1d was not associated to any discontinuity because the fracture crack did not reach that area. Figure 2 a shows specimen GFRP-P031-40-710-16_3/6, which was the one tested beyond 20,000 cycles, and Figs. 2b through f show the scan images discussed for Fig. 1. Although the typical C-scan

showed the places where damage was being created, Fig. 2d again seems show more information. The red coloring penetrated towards the left side of the middle contrast spot, and Fig. 2d also shows spots in the same zone. Although no scan image matched the shape of the red coloring found inside. At cycle 26,079, a confocal microscope was used to observe the middle spot surface. Figures 3 and 4 are an example of the crack found. The surface area to the left in Fig. 3 has been flattened by the contact noses. In Fig. 4, the fabric to the left is largely undamaged, but to the right, a rise of the surface can be observed, and an incipient crack can be noticed.

The last C-scan of specimen CFRP-P021-40-1040-27_1/2 (Fig. 5) shows damage due to the tool contact points, but a visual inspection would conclude the same. However the confocal microscope was used to quantify the damage. A transition region from a normal surface to a scarred surface can be observed in Fig. 6. Different stages of surface damage are shown in Fig. 7, where the resin has been flattened, then the first layer of carbon fibers can be seen, and at the bottom right hand side the second underlying layer is revealed. A close-up of the center region of Fig. 7 is shown in Fig. 8, and clearly indicates that several carbon fibers have broken. Figure 9 is a 3D plot of the center region of Fig. 8, and shows that damage depth in the first carbon fiber layer reaches $20\mu\text{m}$, which is 15% of the thickness to that layer.

Fig.1. In (a) a photo is shown of specimen GFRP-FAT01-P031-SDEF-40-710-16_5/6 that broke at

4001 cycles. In (b) a C-scan at cycle 4000 is shown. And in (c) through (f) different 2D images of the processed A-scan signal are shown.

Fig.2. In (a) a photo is shown of specimen GFRP-FAT01-P031-SDEF-40-710-16_3/6 that broke at 26,504 cycles. In (b) a C-scan at cycle 26,079 is shown. And in (c) through (f) different 2D images of the processed A-scan signal are shown.

Fig.3. A crack can be seen from the digitally stitched confocal image of the middle surface region of specimen GFRP-FAT01-P031-SDEF-40-710-16_3/6. The depth scale ranges $-55.85\mu\text{m}$ to $57.82\mu\text{m}$, and the white horizontal scale is $350\mu\text{m}$.

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Fig.4. The digitally stitched confocal image above shows an area adjacent to the image in Fig. 3. The depth scale ranges $-43.71\mu\text{m}$ to $44.34\mu\text{m}$, and the white horizontal scale is $350\mu\text{m}$.

Fig.7. A confocal image is shown of the surface area next to the image shown in Fig. 6. The depth scale ranges $-90.86\mu\text{m}$ to $96.50\mu\text{m}$, and the white horizontal scale is $350\mu\text{m}$.

Fig.5. The image shows a C-scan of specimen CFRP-P021-40-1040-27_1/2 after 20,000 cycles and shows two vertical spots that coincide with surface damage.

Fig.6. A confocal image is shown of the surface that coincides with the darkest spot in Fig. 5. The depth scale ranges $-163.99\mu\text{m}$ to $168.32\mu\text{m}$, and the white horizontal scale is $350\mu\text{m}$.

Fig.8. A close-up image of Fig. 9 shows broken carbon fibers due to friction with the bending tools. The depth scale ranges $-16.15\mu\text{m}$ to $17.15\mu\text{m}$, and the white horizontal scale is $350\mu\text{m}$.

Fig.9. A 3D confocal image is shown that measures the damage depth into the first carbon fiber layer. The depth scale ranges $-12.61\mu\text{m}$ to $7.39\mu\text{m}$.

5 Conclusions

The additional information (newer spots) produced by the \downarrow -scans still require further trials and comparisons with the actual internal damage. However, the observations of this study seem to point to the \downarrow -scan without the I & B echoes, as the image that can combine the most information both from discontinuities near the I echo and the B echo. Ultrasound inspections in the GFRP of this study helped locate possible surface damage, and confocal microscopy was capable of noticing cracks on that surface. In CFRP specimens the damage was visually evident, but confocal images helped quantify the depth and type of damage.

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